

A Novel Spray Reagent for Flavones and Quinones

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THE present investigation was carried out to find some new spray reagent for detecting the presence of flavones and quinones.

Experimental

The paper chromatograms were developed with butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5 v/v) and sprayed with 1% aqueous solution of borax. The spray reagent does not give colour reaction with completely methylated flavone and 3-hydroxy 3',4',5,7-tetramethoxy flavone. The colour intensity has been found to increase in the case of compounds containing vicinal hydroxyl groups.

This reagent has been found to be equal in performance on comparison with the known spray reagents¹⁻⁵ viz. *p*-toluenesulphonic acid, 25% aqueous lead acetate (basic), 5% aqueous sodium carbonate, methanolic sulphuric acid and 1% methanolic sodium hydroxide solution.

The R_f values and the colour with the spray reagent are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Name of compounds	R_f	Colour observed with the reagent
2-hydroxy 1 : 4 naphthaquinone	0.84	Br
1,8-dihydroxy 3-methyl anthraquinone	0.76	Br
1,8,8-trihydroxy 3-methyl anthraquinone	0.64	LP
1,8-dihydroxy 3-methyl 6-methoxy-anthraquinone	0.94	LP
1,6-dimethoxy 8-hydroxy 3-methyl-anthraquinone	0.11	V
7-hydroxy flavone	0.00	LY
5,7-dihydroxy flavone	0.67	LY
5,7-dihydroxy flavone	0.57	LY
5,7-dihydroxy 4'-methoxy flavone	0.50	Y
5-hydroxy 3',4'-dimethoxy flavone	0.43	LY
5-hydroxy 7,3',4'-trimethoxy flavone	0.38	Y
5,3'-dihydroxy 7,4'-dimethoxy flavone	0.52	Y
3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxy flavonol	0.85	Y
3,5,3',4'-tetrahydroxy 7-methoxy flavonol	0.80	Y
3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxy flavonol	0.78	Y
3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxy flavanone	0.84	LBr
3',5,7-trihydroxy flavone	0.91	Y
5,7,4'-trihydroxy 3,6,3'-trimethoxy flavonol	0.61	LY
3,5,7,3',4'-pentahydroxy flavonol	0.86	LBr
3,5,7,3',4'-pentamethoxy flavonol	0.70	—
3-hydroxy 3',4',5,7-tetramethoxy flavonol	0.88	—
3,5,3',4'-tetrahydroxy flavanone-7-O-galactoside	0.73	Br
5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy flavonol-3-O-rhamnoside	0.82	Y
5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxy flavonol-3-O-rutinoside	0.56	Y

Br=brown, LP=light pink, V=violet, LY=light yellow, Y=yellow, LBr=light brown.

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Ionisation Constants of Some New Substituted Pyridyl Thioureas

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THERE is a general paucity of information regarding acid base equilibria of substituted pyridyl thioureas except for the work of Prasad¹ and Kashyap² who studied the ionisation constants of some substituted pyridyl thioureas. So it was thought desirable to determine the ionisation constants of some N'-2-(substituted-pyridyl)-N-substituted-thioureas and to know the effect of substituents on the thermodynamic ionisation constants of these compounds.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the present studies were of BDH AnalaR quality. The compounds N'-2-(3-hydroxy-pyridyl)-N-phenylthiourea, (HPPTuH); N'-2-(3-hydroxy-pyridyl)-N-*p*-tolylthiourea, (HPPT-TuH); N'-2-(3-hydroxy-pyridyl)-N-*o*-tolylthiourea, (HPOTTuH); N'-2-(3-hydroxy-pyridyl)-N-ethylthiourea, (HPETuH); N'-2-(4-methyl-pyridyl)-N-phenyl-thiourea, (4MPPTuH); N'-2-(4-methyl-pyridyl)-N-*p*-tolyl-thiourea, (4MPPT-TuH); N'-2-(4-methyl-pyridyl)-N-*o*-tolyl-thiourea, (4MPOTTuH); N'-2-(4-methyl-pyridyl)-N-ethyl-thiourea, (4MPE-TuH); N'-2-(6-methyl-pyridyl)-N-phenyl-thiourea, (6MPPTuH); N'-2-(6-methyl-pyridyl)-N-*p*-tolyl-thiourea, (6MPPT-TuH); N'-2-(6-methyl-pyridyl)-N-*o*-tolyl-thiourea, (6MPOTTuH) and N'-2-(6-methyl-pyridyl)-N-ethyl-thiourea, (6MPETuH) were prepared as described earlier³.

These compounds were purified by recrystallization from ethanol. The purity of all these compounds was checked by melting points. The pK_a

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Potential Tuberculostats : Some Products from Malonanilic Acid Hydrazides

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ACID hydrazides and their condensation products have gained prominence as tuberculostatic¹, anti-fungal², antileprotic³ and antihelmintic⁴ agents. Buu-Hoi⁵ *et al* have synthesised a large number of hydrazides and their condensation products with various aldehydes and ketones in view of the possibility of their being less toxic than parent hydrazides due to blocking of the free $-NH_2$ group. A careful literature review has revealed that condensation of fluorine bearing aldehyde with acid hydrazides of malonanilic acid series has not been done so far. Organic compounds having fluorine have shown promise in different fields. The present study records the condensation of *p*-fluorobenzaldehyde with malonanilic acid hydrazides in ethanol and formation of acid hydrazones of the type I.

I

The identity of the products (I) has been established by the elemental analysis and ir spectra.

The ir spectrum of acid hydrazone (I; R=H) shows absorption band of C=N group at 1600 cm^{-1} , N-N group at 1240 cm^{-1} , NH-CO group

at 1630 cm^{-1} and $-CH_2$ group at 1440 cm^{-1} and the band at 780 cm^{-1} confirms *p*-substitution.

Iminophosphinic acids have been found to possess anticancerous properties⁶. In order to study the effect of substituents on physiological activity, three new iminophosphinic acids of type II have been synthesised by the treatment of acid hydrazones(I) with hypophosphorous acid.

II

Oxadiazole moiety is associated with many interesting biological properties and malonanilic acid hydrazides have been scrutinized for anti-tubercular activity. New compounds (III) have been obtained in which two moieties have been fused for the first time by the condensation of 5-phenyl-2-chloroacetamido-1,3,4-oxadiazole with malonanilic acid hydrazides and the products of the type III have been obtained in low yield.

III

Experimental

Malonanilic acid hydrazides were prepared according to the procedure reported in the literature⁷.

Condensation of p-fluorobenzaldehyde with malonanilic acid hydrazone : (I; R=H)

General method : Solutions of *p*-fluorobenzaldehyde (0.124 g; 0.001 mole) in absolute ethanol (1.0 ml) and malonanilic acid hydrazone (0.193 g; 0.001 mole) in ethanol (3.0 ml) were mixed and a drop of concentrated sulphuric acid was added. The mixture was gently boiled for two minutes. On cooling the product separated. Crystallisation from ethanol gave shining silky needles of the acid hydrazone. Yield: 0.23 g (76.9%) m.p. 218°; Found : N, 14.47; F, 6.58%. $C_{16}H_{14}O_2N_3F$ requires N, 14.05; F, 6.23%.

Reaction of malonanilic acid hydrazone of p-fluorobenzaldehyde with hypophosphorous acid : (II; R=H)

General method : Acid hydrazone (0.299 g; 0.001 mole) was dissolved in absolute ethanol (10 ml) and hypophosphorous acid (2.0 g.) was added. Mixture was gently heated for five minutes and set aside for ten minutes. On cooling white solid separated out, which was collected under suction and recrystallised from ethanol in white shining crystals. Yield: 0.25 g (69.3%) m.p. 147°; Found : N, 11.10; F, 5.60%. $C_{16}H_{17}O_4N_3FP$ requires N, 11.50; F, 5.20%.

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